

Drought tolerance

A rapid method for determining plant water stress in upland rice

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Water stress which can limit upland rice production needs to be measured and quantified. Commonly used methods can be grouped into those which measure water content and those which measure water potential.

In 1983 wet season, we used the pressure chamber and leaf disc techniques to determine the water status of rice leaves in the laboratory and on a toposquence on the IRRI upland farm. Leaf-water potential (LWP) was measured by the pressure chamber technique. In the laboratory study, a fully developed leaf, second from the top of the main culm of IR36 plants, was excised at the leaf collar.

Leaves were allowed to dry in air for 1, 3, 5, or 7 min. After drying, each leaf was enclosed in a plastic bag, and LWP measured by the pressure chamber technique, in which the LWP was assumed equal to the equilibrium pressure required to bring water to the cut surface of the leaf collar cross-section. Relative water content (RWC) of each leaf was determined immediately after LWP measurements. Leaf discs, 4-mm-diam, were floated on distilled water to bring the stressed tissues to a fully turgid state. The RWC was determined as the mass of water in the tissue in the dried state relative to the mass held at saturation. In the field study, LWP of rice cultivars ITA235 and IR36 was measured by pressure chamber. Data were for plants grown at 10, 18, 30, 46, and 82 m from the bottom of the toposquence hill slope.

Laboratory findings showed a gradual increase in LWP as drying period increased. Similarly, RWC of the same leaves decreased with drying period, but not so strongly as LWP. In the toposquence study, LWP was strongly dependent on toposquence position, reflecting the drier soil-water conditions at higher slope elevations. ITA235, a typical upland variety from Africa, had higher LWP than the lowland cultivar IR36.

LWP measurement by pressure chamber was more rapid (2-3 min versus 48 h) and convenient than RWC measurement. RWC takes longer because of the hydration procedure. For a drought screening program involving perhaps up to 100 cultivars, LWP as measured by pressure chamber can effectively discriminate among varieties. □

Adverse soils tolerance

Inheritance of salt tolerance in mangrove swamp rice

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In West Africa, traditional mangrove swamp varieties exhibit considerable variability in salt tolerance. Studies on the genetics of salt tolerance will assist breeders in incorporating this character into improved varieties.

We evaluated parents and F_1 , F_2 , B_1 , and B_2 populations of two crosses for salt tolerance by comparing the rate of root growth in normal and in 80 mM NaCl culture solutions. All the generations were tested simultaneously and a tolerance ratio (TR) was calculated for each plant in each population.

The observed values of all the genera-

Table 1. Means, weight, and number of plants tested in each family.

Generation	Pokkali/Djabon			Pa Merr 108A/BG90-2		
	Mean	Weight	No.	Mean	Weight	No.
P_1 =	0.510	2016.807	47	0.505	2181.818	47
P_2 =	0.306	4363.636	47	0.264	1118.012	17
F_1 =	0.433	1322.314	15	0.414	828.402	13
F_2 =	0.515	1458.967	47	0.480	1450.151	47
B_1 =	0.521	788.044	28	0.473	1441.860	30
B_2 =	0.343	558.376	10	0.369	1228.070	20

tion means and their weight, calculated as the reciprocal of the variance of the mean and the number of plants on which the means and variances were based, are in Table 1. The mean TR of F_1 plants from both crosses generally fell between the parental means. Heterosis in the F_2 may suggest the presence of a maternal effect on the progenies.

The minimum model in Table 2 indicated a highly significant additive effect [d] of the homozygous loci. The domi-

nance effect [h] was apparently a major component in the genetic variation of salt tolerance in Pokkali/Djabon, but is nonsignificant in Pa Merr 108A/BG90-2 where the values were very small, indicating some net directional dominance for low tolerance.

Among the three types of epistatic gene effects, [i] (additive \times additive) was the only significant effect. This interaction may be due to the presence of a maternal effect. In the final model in the